

SMS+ : Enhancing SMS One-Time Passwords with Behavioral Biometrics and Motion Data

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Abstract

This work discloses a method for strengthening SMS-based authentication (SMS OTP) through behavioral biometrics and motion sensor analysis. In the proposed SMS+ system, instead of a standard SMS one-time code, the user receives a secure link delivered via SMS. This link opens a browser-based web interface where the user is prompted to type or interact with a short phrase, digits, or code. Typing biometrics / keystroke dynamics, event timing, and mobile motion sensor data (accelerometer, gyroscope) are captured during this process. The system verifies that the SMS recipient's behavioral/typing pattern matches the enrolled user before revealing or validating the OTP, or in some cases authenticating the user without showing the OTP at all. This approach transforms SMS OTP into a phishing-resistant authentication factor. The same method can also secure magic links, push notifications, email codes, mobile apps, QR code links, and similar flows, as long as the URL opens in the mobile browser where the typing challenge is performed. Other behavioral verifications may be applied, as well as methods such as passkeys, local storage, geolocation, or risk-based analysis to determine whether the user should be allowed to view the OTP or complete the protected action that the SMS+ challenge secures.

Background

SMS one-time passwords remain widely deployed as a two-factor authentication method, despite known weaknesses such as SIM swap, device theft, and interception. Existing mitigations (number-porting checks, push notifications) only partially address these vulnerabilities. Behavioral biometrics can provide an inherence factor layered on top of SMS without requiring new hardware or major user workflow changes.

System Description

1. **Message delivery:** The user receives an SMS containing a link to an SMS+ verification page instead of, or in addition to, a numeric OTP (but any type of code/password can be used).

2. **User interaction:** The verification page prompts the user to type a short phrase, code, or number sequence.
 3. **Data capture:** The system records typing biometrics data (keystroke timing, press/hold durations, latency, etc) as well as motion sensor data (from accelerometer, gyroscope) collected during the typing challenge/event.
 4. **Verification:** Captured behavioral data is compared to the user's previously enrolled patterns. If the behavioral match is within threshold, the OTP is revealed or validated, or depending on the use case, the challenge may simply trigger authentication completion, or another step.
 5. **Fallback and reset:** If behavioral verification fails or is unavailable, the system can fall back to other factors or invoke a delayed reset. This delay allows a classic SMS OTP validation only after the user has had time to secure their SIM or accounts. SMS+ may also be reset by admins or through hybrid reset mechanisms. After a successful attempt, users can reset or disable secure codes at any time.
 6. **Initial enrollment:** Users may be required to enroll, or they can opt in during any regular SMS OTP verification. A simple link and call to action such as "turn on secure codes" can be included in an SMS along with the OTP code. Once the link is clicked and the user completes the first challenge, future OTPs are hidden in the SMS. In subsequent uses, the challenge security gradually increases, and each time the user must complete the challenge before the OTP is revealed.
 7. **Extended checks:** Beyond typing and motion data, other behavioral verifications may be applied, as well as methods such as passkeys, local storage, geolocation, or risk-based analysis to decide whether the user should be allowed to view the OTP or complete the protected action.
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Example Embodiments

1. **Mobile-first implementation:** SMS+ link opens a responsive web page that records typing behavior and device motion data before revealing the OTP.
 2. **IAM integration:** SMS+ is integrated into identity platforms (Okta, Auth0, PingOne, Entra) via inline hooks or API connectors, posing as an SMS service provider.
 3. **Banking use case:** During transaction confirmation, the SMS+ challenge ensures that even if a SIM swap attacker, an interceptor, or a phone thief, receives the SMS, they cannot pass behavioral verification.
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Analysis Modes

- **Challenge Mode:** Only successful behavioral verification allows access to the OTP, effectively turning SMS into a phishing-resistant factor.
- **Fallback Mode:** Users may still complete authentication with legacy OTP validation if behavioral checks fail, depending on policy.

Applications

- Stronger SMS OTP authentication in banking, fintech, healthcare and domains where security is important but SMS is still used for authentication for the lack of a stronger method.
- Integration with identity and access management systems, or SMS providers as an enhanced SMS factor.
- Fraud prevention, reducing risk of SIM swap, device theft, interception/MITM and malware attacks.

Novelty

Unlike prior art that only delivers numeric OTP codes, SMS+ requires an interaction that produces behavioral and motion data for biometric verification. This approach uniquely preserves SMS as a familiar channel while elevating it to multi-factor strength, making it resistant to common attacks such as SIM swaps, phone theft, SMS interception or device malware attacks.